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**FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE MECHANISMS OF PROVIDING STATE AID
AND SUPPORT FOR BUSINESSES IN UZBEKISTAN**

**ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ МЕХАНИЗМОВ
ПРЕДОСТАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ СУБЪЕКТАМ
МАЛОГО БИЗНЕСА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

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Abstract. In this paper looked through reforms held in improving the business environment and government support for small business and private entrepreneurship. Also, analyzed the role of “Single window” principle of providing public services, additionally given changes in “Doing Business” Ranking of World bank.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются реформы, проводимые для улучшения бизнес-среды и государственная поддержка малого бизнеса и частного предпринимательства. Также анализируется роль «Единого окна» как принципа предоставления государственных услуг. Дополнительно приводятся изменения в Рейтинге Всемирного банка “Doing Business”.

Keywords: business, small business, private entrepreneurship, government support, single window, public services.

Ключевые слова: бизнес, малый бизнес, частное предпринимательство, государственная поддержка, Единое окно, коммунальные услуги.

Today, small business and private entrepreneurship (SBPE) has great significance in terms of the country’s social and economic development.

We can see that when the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov gave a speech about the country’s socio-economic development in 2015 and the most important priorities of economic program for 2016 in the meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers, where he mentioned that “*The prime objective of ours is in spite of the current difficulties, to continue reforms and structural changes in the economy, private property, at the expense of small businesses provided with greater opportunities and to move ahead*” (1) and also he especially expressed that we should improve public services, small business and protect the interests of private business,

government, law enforcement and regulatory authorities in the relations with the introduction of the principle of the supremacy of the rights of entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship, simplify and facilitate the functioning of the organization, protect the legal rights of private property owners and entrepreneurs, strengthen their guarantees the role of the courts in addressing the issue of special attention to support SBPE [1].

Reforms in developing small business and private entrepreneurship

Taking into account the above, many opportunities for the development of SBPE have been created, namely:

- To simplify and facilitate the functioning of the organization of businesses, more than 40 regulatory changes and additions to the document have been implemented.

- If a business entity is in violation of tax and customs legislation, the norm of law has been established indicating that the property could be confiscated only in accordance with the decision of the court, the terms of considering a lawsuit introduced were significantly reduced.

- Now the micro and small enterprises and farming activities are inspected once every four years, and other business activities are inspected once every three years in order to check and control bodies such inspections only be carried out in accordance with the decision of the Coordination Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

- administrative responsibility was strengthened for such cases when the activity and the bank accounts of entrepreneurs are illegally ceased, information about the funds in their bank accounts are unreasonably required and when businessmen are forced to allocate funds in charity and other works.

- The legal mechanism was launched guaranteeing to cover the full amount of damages including lost profits experienced by business entities as a result of action or inaction of state agencies, local self-government bodies' illegal decisions by officials.

- Due to the introduction of electronic forms in relationship between the government and businesses in 2015, 42800 business entities were registered in the portal of online public services via the Internet. They have access to 260 types of interactive services.

- From January 1, 2016 in all regions of the entrepreneurs, “single window” principle of providing public services on the basis of the only centers was launched (1).

Role and successes of single window services

Businesses by the use of modern information and communication technologies in order to improve the quality and accessibility of public services and to ensure transparency, the establishment of around 194 “single window” centers is given in the Decree No. UP-4725 on May 15, 2015 by the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov based on “To ensure the protection of private property, small business and measures to eliminate barriers to the rapid development of them”.

Single window service center receives businesses statements in the following order (Table 1):

1. Taking turn
2. Waiting Queue
3. Giving the application
4. The acceptance of the application and registration of it in EICS (*Electronic interagency collaborative system*)
5. Giving the receipt confirming the acceptance of the documents
6. Scanning the application and its all attachments
7. Sending the application to the competent authorities
8. Consideration of the application
9. Providing the results of the consideration
10. Giving the result to “single window” center
11. The results and registration
12. inform the complainant of the results

13. Giving the result to the applicant

Time distribution: 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6-points — 30 minutes; 6 and 7-points — during the day the application received; 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 and 13-points — in the space of set period of time (2).

Table 1.

THE SERVICES PROVIDED FOR BUSINESS ENTITIES BY THE PRINCIPLES OF “SINGLE WINDOW”

№	<i>The name of the service</i>
1.	Connecting business entities to ready to use communications systems.
2.	Deciding to change the external appearance of buildings and structures (repair the dorms).
3.	Allowing the reconstruction and re-specialization of the buildings and structures.
4.	Allowing the implementation of the construction works.
5.	The certificate of state registration of the land plots.
6.	Giving the state registration of the rights issue of building, construction and perennial trees.
7.	Giving the state registration for issues related to mortgage and construction of buildings and structures, as well as proprietary rights to the land parcel and trade agreements.
8.	Giving the right to engage in retail trade in alcoholic products with licenses.
9.	Giving the right with the license to sell alcohol in public eating-places.
10.	Giving the right with the license to carry out a portable trade.
11.	Allowing the placement of outdoor advertising.
12.	Permitting turning the category of residential premises into non-residential ones.
13.	Giving conclusions that disturbed re-cultivation was done in lands during the use of underground deposits.
14.	Permission to cut trees in the forest in areas not covered by the fund.
15.	Special permission to water consumption and use.
16.	Special permission to the use of objects of plant world

Source: (2)

To assess the business climate in 189 countries around the world on the basis of the same criteria, the World Bank’s “Doing Business” calculating ease of doing business ranking is compiled each year. Countries are assessed based on the methodology of 10 indicators (Table 2).

Table 2.

THE PLACE OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE WORLD BANK'S “DOING BUSINESS” RANKING

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>“Doing business” — 2015</i>	<i>“Doing business” — 2016</i>
Ease of doing business	141	87
The implementation of the agreements	32	32
The creation of new ventures	64	42
Taking loans	105	42
Solving issues related to economic impoverishment	75	75
The state registration of real property	113	87
The protection of minority investors	87	88
Electrical connection	108	112
Paying taxes	117	115
Permissions for constructions	149	151
Leading foreign trade	158	159

Source: (2).

“Doing Business 2016” report of The World Bank in October 2015, Uzbekistan’s place changed from 141 to 87 in the ranking of the podium. During the last year, at least three reforms were implemented, and Uzbekistan is now among 10 most progressive reformer countries (2).

Conclusion

We believe that our country's achievements in the field of business are directly linked to the development of entrepreneurship and benefits as well as opportunities created by the government and play a key role in the life of business entities.

The year 2017 has been named as “The year of dialogue with people and human interests” with the initiative of the President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, and the credit demands of citizens have been investigating by banks in order to make every citizen of the country to set up their own business under the slogan “Making common population entrepreneur” and banks have been providing practical assistance in the implementation of the projects for those who wish to engage in business. As a result of these noble works and opportunities, the development of small business and entrepreneurship in our country will improve further.

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